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ABSTRACT

BOOK

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The Power of Sorghum Farmer Corporation As Strengthening National Food Security

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Abstract

The cultivation and development of sorghum plants is the government's effort in strengthening national food security. Sorghum can substitute wheat where Indonesia is the world's largest wheat importer as much as 10-11 million tons a year. The acceleration of sorghum cultivation is carried out by the government by cooperating with appointed private parties, one of which is PT H2O (Holistic Health business Opportunity) Group Indonesia. In its idea, PT H2O developed a farmer-based sorghum farming area with a pilot project in the Semarijo Area (Sumberjati Village, Rejosari Village, Manting Village and Jembul Village), Pacet District, Mojokerto Regency. Farmer Corporation is one of the government's efforts in improving the welfare of farmers as stated in Minister of Agriculture of the Republic of Indonesia regulation No. 18/Permentan/RC.040/4/1018. This research aims at farmer corporations developed by PT H2O Group Indonesia from the aspects of management and communication established with its stakeholders. The research method used is qualitative descriptive to obtain as much data as possible with data collection techniques through in-depth interviews and field observations for 3 months. The result is the development of farmer corporation-based agricultural areas carried out by PT H2O Group Indonesia (Holistic Health business Opportunity) is (1) unique, solid and controlled internal management, (2) establishing effective communication of all stakeholders by establishing mutualist partnerships (3) this farmer corporation is able to empower the community and the development of agricultural areas can go hand in hand so as to improve the welfare of sorghum farmers. Thus, this system is able to improve the welfare of farmers and Indonesia is able to be self-sufficient in food and enter the international market.

Keywords: Sorghum, Farmer Corporation, National Food Security

The Influence Of Compensation And Work Environment On Employee Performance Through Job Satisfaction As An Intervening Variable

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Abstract

This research aims to analyze the influence of compensation and work environment on employee performance both directly and indirectly through job satisfaction as an intervening variable. This research uses quantitative research using an explanatory research approach. Where the sample in this research was 46 employees at UD. New Jaya Sakti who were taken using saturated sampling. This research has seven hypotheses and where are the seven hypotheses. The results of the simultaneous test show that compensation and work environment influence job satisfaction. Then compensation, work environment and job satisfaction influence employee performance. The results of the hypothesis test also show that there are five paths that have a significant effect, namely compensation on employee performance of 0.449 with a significance value of 0.000, compensation on job satisfaction of 0.476 with a significance of 0.000, job satisfaction on employee performance of 0.274 with a significance value of 0.023, work environment on Job satisfaction is 0.565 with a significance value of 0.000. The work environment on employee performance is 0.529 with a significance value of 0.000. This research also proves two indirect paths showing the effect of compensation on employee performance through job satisfaction of 0.130 and the work environment on employee performance through job satisfaction of 0.154.

Keywords: Compensation, Work Environment, Job Satisfaction, Employee Performance

Direct Marketing Analysis In Increasing Sales Volume At Sensory Coffee Roastery, Panti District, Jember Regency

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Abstract

Sensory Coffee Roastery markets its products directly for sake improve the quality of Sensory Coffee Roastery products. In addition, the impact of direct marketing to the increasing volume of product sales Sensory Coffee Roastery. The purpose of this research is to analyze direct marketing and the impact of direct marketing on sales volume Sensory Coffee Roastery. The method used in this research is descriptive method using a qualitative approach. The resulting product Sensory Coffee Roastery is the ideal liberica, robusta and Arabica Coffee the flavors can be combined into one by using a pouch or dip packaging which is the main attraction of Sensory Coffee Sensory products. Results of this research in the form of an update on the direct marketing strategy that carried out by Sensory Coffee Roastery in increasing volume production sales, including face-to-face marketing strategies (personal selling), kiosk marketing, catalog marketing, telemarketing and online marketing. In addition to the marketing strategy, the need for production locations The newest one, which is located in a more strategic location, was discovered by the wider community.

Keywords: Direct Marketing, Sales Volume, Dip Coffee

the influence of personal selling and publicity on increasing sales volume

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Abstract

Increase in sales volume is the amount of sales achieved within a company in a certain time period. Factors that influence increasing sales volume are personal selling and publicity. The aim of this research is to determine the effect of personal selling and publicity on increasing sales volume both directly and indirectly (at CV Raja Tani Makmur). This research is quantitative research with associative research type. The sample in this study consisted of 30 respondents. Data collection methods use observation, questionnaires and interviews. The analysis method is multiple linear regression assisted by IBM 24 software. The research results show that. 1. Personal selling and publicity have a significant influence on increasing sales volume. 2 Personal selling has a positive and significant effect on increasing sales volume. 3. Publicity has a positive and significant effect on increasing sales volume.

Keywords: Personal Selling, Publicity and Increase in Sales Volume

The influence of public services on community satisfaction at the Bonto Bahari sub-district office, Bulukumba district

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Abstract

The type of research used is quantitative research aims to describe research objects or research results through data or sample, data collection techniques used were observation, questionnaires and documentation. The method in this research uses analytical methods simple regression with hypothesis testing, namely the T test. The number of samples is 100 people using the Simple Random Sampling Method. Based on The statistical results of the t test for the variable quality of public services obtained levels significance of 4.064 t table 1.984 which successfully proves that "The quality of public services has a significant effect on satisfaction community at the Bonto Bahari sub-district office, Bulukumba Regency. Statistically it can It is shown that the quality of public services does have an influence which is significant for community satisfaction at the Bonto Bahari sub-district office in Bonto Bahari District, Bulukumba Regency.

Keywords: service quality, community satisfaction

The influence of Communication Skills and HR Competence on Employee Work Effectiveness at the Gowa Regency Education Office

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Abstract

The background to this research is that the percentage of communication at the Gowa district education office; not good. From the problems above, it can be identified that the problems that arise are a lack of human resource capability, a lack of communication which hinders work effectiveness. This research uses questionnaire observation, then the research tests hypotheses about the relationship and cause and effect between the variables to be studied by referring to predetermined hypotheses, with a quantitative approach that emphasizes testing theory through measuring variables using numbers and carrying out analysis using statistical calculations. Meanwhile, the data analysis technique uses non-parametric statistics and in order to obtain effective and accurate results when carrying out correlation analysis between the independent variable and the dependent variable, in this research the author uses computer tools with the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 19.0) program. In research conducted on 65 respondents taken from all employees at the Gowa Regency Education Office, they distributed 30 statements aimed at finding out opinions about the Influence of Communication and Human Resource Capabilities on Work Effectiveness at the Gowa Regency Education Office. After conducting research and carrying out statistical tests supported by quantitative data, the influence between the variables in this research was obtained and a hypothesis test was carried out between communication and human resource capabilities on work effectiveness at the Gowa Regency Education Office. The relationship between each of the two variables on Work Effectiveness is Linear Positive. Meanwhile, the influence of communication and human resource capabilities on work effectiveness at the Gowa Regency Education Office is 66.8%, while the remaining 33.2% is influenced by other factors not discussed in this research.

Keywords: communication, human resource competency, work effectiveness

Accountability and Transparency in the Management of Village Fund Allocation (ADD) in Jatiroto Sumberbaru District Jember Regency

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Abstract

This research was conducted to identify and describe the accountability and transparency in the management of village fund allocations in Jatiroto village, Sumberbaru district, Jember Regency for the fiscal year 2022, and to determine whether it complies with Jember Regency Regulation Number 11 of 2022 and Ministry of Home Affairs Regulation Number 20 of 2018. This research is a qualitative research, utilizing both primary and secondary data. The analysis method used in this study was qualitative descriptive analysis, with data collection methods encompassing observation, interviews, and documentation. The research findings indicate that the management of the Village Fund Allocation in Jatiroto village is satisfactory and compliant with Jember Regency Regulation Number 11 of 2022 and Ministry of Home Affairs Regulation Number 20 of 2018. The management of the Village Fund Allocation in Jatiroto village has been conducted based on the principles of transparency, accountability, participation, and balance, and the village apparatus has periodically reported the implementation of the village fund allocation to the higher-level government. The transparency in managing the village fund allocation in Jatiroto village aligns with Ministry of Home Affairs Regulation Number 20 of 2018, evidenced by the conduct of Musrenbangdes (village development planning meetings) and the display of banners detailing proposed work programs up to budget realization.

Keywords: accountability; transparency; village fund allocation

The Influence of Financial Literacy and E-Commerce on MSME Performance in Makassar City

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Abstract

This research aims to examine the influence of financial literacy and e-commerce on the performance of MSMEs in Makassar City. The type of research used in this research is a quantitative survey method. The MSME sample consisted of 100 samples selected using the purposive sampling method. The data in the sample uses primary data obtained using a distributed questionnaire. The data analysis methods used are validation tests, reliability tests, multiple linear regression tests and hypothesis tests using the SPSS 26 analysis tool. The research results show that financial literacy and e-commerce have a positive and significant effect on the performance of MSMEs in Makassar City.

Keywords: financial literacy; e-commerce; MSME performance

The Affect Of Profitability, Leverage And Company Size On Enterprise Value In Financial Industry Section Company In BEI 2021-2022

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Abstract

This study aims to test the effect of profitability, leverage, and corporate size on corporate value. The research population includes all financial sector companies registered with the BEI for 2021-2022. This study sample was obtained using the purposive sampling method, in which only 32 financial sector companies registered with the BEI met all criteria, so 64 data were used as research samples. This study used multiple regression models to test the effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable. The results of this study show that corporate profitability, leverage, and size partially affect corporate value.

Keywords: Profitability; Leverage; Company Size; Company Value

Clustering Analysis on Financial Literacy, Digital Literacy, and Digital Financial Literacy of Emerging Adults (Gen Z) Investors in Rural East Java

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Abstract

This research explores the literacy profiles of emerging adults in rural Java, focusing on financial, digital information, and digital financial literacy. Through clustering analysis, five distinct classes emerge, each showcasing unique strengths and areas for improvement. The findings highlight the diversity within the demographic, emphasizing the need for tailored educational approaches. "Tech Savvy" individuals excel in digital realms but lag in financial literacy, suggesting a potential for technology-focused interventions. Conversely, "Financial Ace" individuals demonstrate above-average financial literacy but require improvement in digital and informational aspects. Age-appropriate and comprehensive literacy programs are recommended, addressing specific needs identified in each class. The insights contribute to a nuanced understanding of literacy dynamics among emerging adults, guiding policymakers and educators in creating effective and inclusive literacy enhancement programs.

Keywords: Gen Z; Investors; Financial literacy; Digital investing; Clustering profiles

Quantification Of The Impact Of Climate Change In Financial Reports: An Ambition Towards Net Zero Emissions

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Abstract

Climate change is one of the big problems facing the world. The special report on Global Warming of 1.5°C shows that achieving zero emissions by mid-century is an important thing to do. The importance of addressing climate change drove global cooperation that led to the signing of the Paris Agreement in 2015. Closing the gap between current climate change mitigation policies and the policies needed to achieve the Paris Agreement temperature targets requires a significant increase in policy ambition. This article argues that policy actions aimed at achieving zero emission levels can be carried out by setting an effective carbon price, the relevance and materiality of climate change issues in financial reports, as well as knowing the strategy for quantifying climate change issues in financial reports based on applicable SAK.

Keywords: financial reports, net zero carbon

Pesantrenpreneur: Realise the Economic Independence of Pesantren (Field Study at Muhammadiyah Boarding School Al-Islam Paleran)

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Abstract

The development of Islam in Indonesia cannot be separated from the development of pesantren education. In fact, pesantren education was born earlier than formal education such as schools or madrasas. Islamic boarding school itself is unique when compared to other formal education systems. The independence of pesantren in the economic field has enormous and sustainable potential if it can be managed properly. This can be seen from the number of students in a pesantren and the number of their needs. If the pesantren can provide and fulfil the basic needs of the students, then this condition can be a great economic potential for the pesantren. Especially if the pesantren can enlarge the market by producing a certain product and circulating it to the community outside the pesantren, the economic potential of the pesantren is even greater. One of the pesantren that develops this economic potential is Muhammadiyah Boarding School (MBS) Al-Islam Paleran. Muhammadiyah Boarding School Al-Islam Paleran is one of the institutions under Muhammadiyah that implements the pesantren system. MBS has several business units that are managed directly by the students, ranging from cooperative business units to processed food products that are marketed to the general public. Some of these business units are efforts made by MBS Al-Islam in optimising the economic potential of the pesantren and the surrounding community. This research is a field research using qualitative approach method, and analysed using descriptive analysis method. The data sources in this study used primary data sources in the form of information from interviews with pesantren administrators, and secondary data obtained from reading journals and theories relevant to this research. The data collection method was carried out using interviews, observation, and documentation. The data is processed as scientific rules in general to answer the formulation of predetermined problems.

Keywords: Muhammadiyah Boarding School; Pesantren Independence; Pesantrenpreneur

Technological Innovation: IoT-based Smart Greenhouse for Optimizing Red Garlic Growth

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Abstract

Red garlic become a reliable commodity in Jember society. Red garlic farmers often face some emerging problems such as the influence of extreme weather on the growth of red garlic crops. The success of growing garlic depends on several factors including maintenance temperature, soil humidity, nutrition and use of medicines. (fungicide). One of the technological developments that can be used in agriculture is the development of greenhouses as a monitoring and control system to control the growth of garlic crops. The presence of this innovation is expected to help carry out automatic spraying, irrigation, medication activities using an Internet of Things-based application system. Components used in this system are Arduino and ESP32 microcontroller, Dht22 sensor as temperature controller, Y1-69 soil moisture sensor, and soil pH sensor to monitor soil fertilizer elements. The device can monitor soil humidity, temperature, medication, and soil pH through the Blynk app. From the results of this study, plants grown in greenhouses have a 100% presentation rate with 30 seeds and are growing fertile. This is better than planting on caterpillars and polybags with a growth rate of 84% and 90% or only 25 seed and 27 seed remains.

Keywords: Red Garlic; Soil Moisture Sensor; Soil PH Sensor; Internet of Things

Disclosure of Carbon Emissions and Their Impact in Company Financial Accounting

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Abstract

Disclosure of carbon emissions provides an explanation of the company's efforts to reduce carbon emissions, such as calculating the energy released, environmental costs and company regulations regarding energy consumption. Carbon emissions disclosures are included in corporate intent reports. The aim of this research is to study the nature of carbon emissions and the brightness of their identification, differences in investors' reactions to different companies. Express carbon emissions symbolically and substantively. This research uses the Mann-Whitney simple regression analysis and testing method. The population in this study are energy sector companies listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange. The sampling technique for the selected companies used purposive sampling. The research results show that there are two characteristics of coal emissions in the sample companies, both symbolic and substantive. Investor feedback for companies divided into different highly symbolic and important groups Companies symbolically declaring carbon emissions received more investor responses than companies that did Disclosure of carbon emissions content.

Keywords: carbon Emission Disclosure, carbon accounting in Indonesia, corporate carbon accounting reporting

Utilization Of Financial Literacy, Digital Literacy, And Efficacy To Improve Msme Performance In Makassar City

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Abstract

This research aims to understand the use of financial literacy, digital literacy and the efficacy of the MSME community to improve the performance of MSMEs. This research uses a quantitative approach with the data source used is primary data obtained from MSME business actors. The sample used in this research is this research involving 30 respondents from MSME business actors. The results of this research show that partially financial literacy does not have a significant positive effect on the performance of MSMEs. Digital literacy has a significant positive effect on the performance of MSMEs. Meanwhile, the effect of efficacy does not have a significant positive effect on the performance of MSME.

Keywords: Financial Literacy, Digital Literacy, and the Efficacy of the MSME Community on MSME Performance

Financial Literacy And Financial Attitude And Their Influence On Financial Management Behavior

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Abstract

This research was conducted to obtain empirical evidence on how financial literacy and financial attitude influence financial management behavior, especially in the MSME Food and Beverage sector in the city of Makassar. The type of research used is quantitative with the population in this research being MSME actors in the food and beverage sector in the city of Makassar, totaling 5,400 BEI with a sample size of 120 samples taken by purposive sampling. Hypothesis testing using SPSS. This research uses multiple linear regression analysis techniques. The results of this research indicate that financial literacy (X1) has an influence on financial management behavior (Y) and Financial Attitude (X2) has an influence on financial management behavior (Y). The data collection method was carried out by distributing questionnaires to MSME actors in the food and beverage sector in the city of Makassar.

Keywords: Financial Literacy , Financial Attitude And Financial Management Behavior

The Influence of the Quality of Financial Accounting Learning and Academic Achievement on the Financial Self-Efficacy of University Accounting Students Muhammadiyah Makassar

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Abstract

This research aims to determine: (1) the influence of the quality of financial accounting learning on financial self-efficacy, (2) the influence of academic achievement on financial self-efficacy. The population in this study was 226 accounting students from the class of 2020, the research sample was 69 students with sample determination using the Slovin formula. The method used is multiple linear regression analysis with the help of SPSS Version 26. Based on the research results, it shows that the Quality of Financial Accounting Learning has no partial effect on Financial Self Efficacy. Meanwhile, Academic Achievement partially influences Financial Self Efficacy.

Keywords: Quality of financial accounting learning, academic achievement, financial self-efficacy, accounting students.

The Influence of Fraud Hexagon in Detecting Financial Statement Fraud on Pharmaceutical Companies Listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange 2018-2022

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Abstract

This study aims to understand the effects of hexagon fraud models in particular pressure, capability, rationalization, arrogance, and collusion on financial reporting cheating. The population of this study includes pharmaceutical companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) from 2018 to 2022. This study used secondary data, namely financial statements and annual reports. Based on the purposive sampling method, the number of companies sampled in this study was 16 out of a total of 31 listed companies and analyzed by multiple linear regression analysis using the SPSS 22 program. The results of this study show that the factors of pressure, capability, rationalization, arrogance, and collusion are not completely significant in the financial statements conducted by pharmaceutical companies listed in the 2018-2022 period.

Keywords: Fraud Hexagon Model; Fraudulent Financial Statements

Construction Of Financial Statements Based On Msme Financial Accounting Standards Using Microsoft Excel At Nusa Mandiri Group

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Abstract

A company needs to prepare financial reports so that a company can run efficiently and effectively. The purpose of this study is to reconstruct the financial statements of the Nusa Mandiri Group in Bondowoso Regency so as to create financial statements that are in accordance with the Financial Accounting Standards for Micro, Small and Medium Entities. The research was conducted in April 2023 and took place at Nusa Mandiri Group. Data collection techniques in this study were interviews, documentation, and observation. Nusa Mandiri Group only records cash out and in and has not recorded financial statements in accordance with the Financial Accounting Standards for Micro, Small and Medium Entities. It is hoped that the Nusa Mandiri Group can develop a better financial report design.

Keywords: Reconstruction, Financial Accounting Standards, Nusa Mandiri Group

Factors That Affect the Timeliness of Financial Report Submission in Manufacturing Companies Listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange 2020-2022

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Abstract

Timeliness in submitting financial reports is an important factor in presenting relevant information. Financial reports that are submitted on time have significant value in decision making. Timeliness of financial reporting is one of the qualitative characteristics that must be met in the presentation of financial statements, as stipulated in Law No. 8 of 1995 concerning Capital Markets. The accounting profession also recognizes the importance of timeliness in submitting financial reports. The results of this study revealed some important findings. First, company size has a significant influence on the timeliness of financial report submission. Large companies tend to be faster in submitting financial reports because they have resources, accounting staff, and strong internal control systems. Second, the reputation of the Public Accounting Firm (KAP) also affects the timeliness of reporting. Companies with a good KAP reputation tend to be more disciplined in submitting financial reports. However, auditor opinion does not have a significant effect on the timeliness of reporting. Third, company age does not affect the timeliness of reporting. Old or young companies can have the same performance in terms of timeliness. Finally, public ownership has no significant effect on the timeliness of financial report reporting. Ownership that is spread in a small percentage results in shareholders having limited power and influence in overseeing the company's management performance.

Keywords: Company Size, Reputation of KAP, Auditor's Opinion, Age of the Company, Public Ownership, Timeliness.

Effect Of Dimenation Good Corporate Governance On Service Company Business Performance

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Abstract

This research is a type of research with an approach explanatory research which aims to test the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The type of data used in this research is quantitative data obtained from financial reports of service companies in the hotel, restaurant and tourism sector (2018-2021). Data sources used in data collection include secondary data. Based on the results of this research, it proves that the board of commissioners, board of directors and audit committee have no influence on the business performance of service companies. This research also proves that the board of commissioners, board of directors and audit committee simultaneously do not have a significant effect on the business performance of service companies.

Keywords: Agency Theory, Good Corporate Governance, Company Business Performance

The Influence of Fraud Hexagon Theory on Detecting Fraudulent Factors in Financial Reports of State-Owned Companies Listed on the IDX 2018-2022

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Abstract

Financial statement fraud is a paradigm that often occurs in Indonesia and causes many losses. Therefore, the aim of this research is to detect the emergence of potential fraud in financial reports using the hexagon fraud theory. In the hexagon fraud theory, there are six dominant factors that can trigger fraud in financial reports: pressure, opportunity, rationalization, ability, arrogance, and collusion. Pressure is proxied by financial targets, financial stability, and financial need; opportunity is proxied by the nature of industry and ineffective monitoring; rationalization is proxied by a change auditor as a proxy for capability to become and change in director; arrogance is proxied by political connections and the frequent number of CEOs; and collusion is proxied by projects with the government. In this research, the dependent variable is measured using the Jones model. The purposeful sampling technique was used in this research in order to obtain a population sample with the criteria of state-owned companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during the last 5 years, namely, 2018–2022. The quantitative method is supported by multiple regression analysis techniques using the SPSS 26 analysis tool in this research. The results of this research show that the variables financial target, financial stability, personal financial need, nature of industry, ineffective monitoring, change in auditor, change in directors, and political connection have no influence on the potential for fraudulent financial statements. Frequent CEO pictures and collaboration projects with the government have a positive and significant effect on the potential for fraudulent financial statements.

Keywords: Fraud, Financial Reports, Fraud Hexagon

Rubbish, Rubbish Everywhere: Checking the accountability of local government performance with photography

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Abstract

Indonesia with its large population, faces waste problems due to increasing population growth and consumption patterns. Improper waste management can pollute the environment, affect aesthetics, and lead to soil and water pollution. The waste problem in Makassar, Indonesia, is a result of ineffective government programs and lack of socialization and awareness. This has led to an accumulation of waste that causes pollution and affects the quality of life in society. The role and awareness of the community, as well as the Makassar City Environmental Service, are crucial in managing waste to create a clean and comfortable environment. The research methodology used qualitative research methods with a descriptive approach to collect detailed information on waste management by the local government. The study used primary data sources through interviews and secondary data sources from the internet and journals. In conclusion, the waste problem in Makassar is a result of ineffective government programs and lack of socialization and awareness. Waste management is crucial for creating a clean and comfortable environment, and the government needs to maximize its budget and management to prevent environmental pollution effectively.

Keywords: Waste, accountability, local government performance, environmental cleanliness

Classification of heart failure using adaboost classifier

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Abstract

Heart Failure causes 287,000 deaths per year. This disease occurs when the heart fails to pump blood according to the metabolic needs of the body's tissues. The prevalence of heart disease occurred in 1,017,290 Indonesians, with the highest number of sufferers being in West Java with 186,809 sufferers and the lowest number in North Kalimantan with 2,733 sufferers. In Indonesia, this disease is the second cause of death after stroke, with a percentage of 12.9%. Half of heart failure sufferers die within five years of diagnosis. Adaboost is one of the boosting algorithms that increase classification performance by combining weak classifier into strong classifier. Firstly, each sample on adaboost has the same weight. The weight of the incorrect result increases and the weight of the correct result decreases. These steps will be repeated until the threshold is fulfilled or the cycle number is maximum. In this study, adaptive boosting (adaboost) was used to classify heart failure disease. The dataset consists of 13 features and 918 observations, which consists of 12 attributes and one of them, that is death_event is a decision class. The features are age, anemia, creatinine_phosphokinase, diabetes, ejection fraction, high_blood_pressure, platelets, serum_creatinine, serum_sodium, sex, smoking, time, and death_event. In this study, we do not establish specific dataset preparation, i.e. preprocessing data. Since there is no missing value, or any other anomaly in this dataset. The performance of Adaboost to classify were measured by accuracy value is 82,22 %, precision value is 72,41%, recall value is 72,41%, AUC score value is 69%.

Keywords: heart failure; adaboost; disease; classifier;

Analysis of Anxiety Levels in End-Stage Kidney Disease Patients Under Dialysis Therapy

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Abstract

End-stage renal disease has a profound impact on both the physiological and psychological aspects of patients. The consequences of end-stage renal disease extend to anxiety, influenced by the symptoms encountered and the side effects resulting from hemodialysis therapy, which, in turn, affects life expectancy and adherence to disease management. This study aims to investigate anxiety levels in individuals with chronic kidney disease undergoing dialysis. This descriptive analytic study involved a total of 45 respondents undergoing hemodialysis therapy at Jember Klinik Hospital. The instruments utilized included an observational form and the Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale. The findings revealed varying levels of anxiety, with severe anxiety at 33.3%, moderate anxiety at 31.1%, mild anxiety at 22.2%, and no anxiety at 13.3%. In the anxiety variable, among the 14 observation items on the HARS instrument, the most pronounced disturbances were observed in tension, depression, cardiovascular symptoms, and respiratory symptoms. Anxiety remains a prevalent psychological symptom among many end-stage renal patients. Strategies should be implemented to mitigate anxiety in patients, thereby improving their quality of life and reducing mortality

Keywords: Anxiety, End Stage Renal Disease, Dialysis

Intensified sugarcane bagasse and rice husk mixture delignification powered by autoclave and microwave

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Abstract

Sugarcane bagasse contains fiber consisting of lignin, cellulose and hemicellulose which is a by-product of the sugar production. Husk is an abundant waste from rice milling as a food crop which is consumed by around most of the Asian population as a staple food. Delignification is a preliminary treatment of lignocellulosic raw materials to facilitate the release of cellulose and hemicellulose. In this study it was carried out with NaOH (alkaline) solution using an autoclave and microwave. This research aims to investigate the reduction of lignin in a mixture of agricultural waste, namely sugarcane bagasse and rice husks. With an autoclave at 121 oC, the lowest lignin was obtained at 5.6% with 30 minutes of treatment. Meanwhile, with a 100 W microwave, the lowest lignin was obtained at 14% in 4 minutes of treatment. The cellulose content in the mixture increased after delignification treatment, from initially only 36% to a maximum of 64% with microwave for 4 minutes. This can facilitate and increase yields in the use of cellulose from a mixture of lignocellulosic materials, especially sugarcane bagasse and rice husks.

Keywords: Sugarcane Bagasse, Rice Husk, Delignification, Microwave, Autoclave

Commerce : A Glimmer Hope for MSMEs Development

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the effect of e-commerce on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) Income in Baubau City. The research was conducted on 83 MSMEs in Baubau. The research used Partial Least Square (PLS) as data analysis. The results show that there is a positive and significant influence of the use of e-commerce on increasing the income of MSMEs, which means that the higher the use of e-commerce in MSMEs, the higher the income of MSMEs in Baubau City. The implication of this research is that it will help MSMEs develop their products and provide information to the Cooperatives Department about the importance of e-commerce in increasing the income of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Baubau City

Keywords: e-commerce; MSME; Income

The Influence Of Brand Ambassador, Tagline, WOM, Tangible And Assurance On Purchasing Decisions At Shopee Among Housewives In Jember Regency

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Abstract

Shopee is a marketplace that is in great demand by consumers in Indonesia. One of the consumers targeted by Shopee is housewives who actually play a large role in purchasing decisions for needed products, especially products for family needs. This research examines the partial and simultaneous influence of the independent variables Brand Ambassador, Tagline, WOM, Tangible and Assurance on purchasing decisions at Shopee. The respondents in this study were housewives who used Shopee in the Jember Regency area. The exact number of the population cannot be known, the sampling technique was purposive sampling of 60 respondents. Testing starts from instrument data testing, classical assumption testing, multiple linear regression analysis, determination testing and finally hypothesis testing. Research findings show that the WOM and Tangible variables have a significant influence on purchasing decisions, which means that housewives in Jember when making purchases at Shopee tend to look at physical evidence and references from previous buyers before they make purchasing decisions. The sig value of WOM and tangible is 0.000 and this value is below the probability value of 0.05, meaning that there is indeed a significant influence. The calculated sig F value is also worth 0.000 and this value is below the probability value of 0.05, which means that simultaneously the five independent variables influence the dependent variable on purchasing decisions.

Keywords: WOM; Tangible ; Shopee; Housewife; Jember.

The Role Of Kiyai In The Development Of Halal Tourism And Culinary In Islamic Boarding Schools

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Abstract

In its development, Islamic boarding schools experience transformation and evolution in accordance with the needs and developments of the times. Basically, Islamic boarding schools are a place for religious learning and a center for Islamic preaching. However, in its development, Islamic boarding schools continue to innovate and be creative in order to survive and serve the educational needs of the community. One innovation is that Islamic boarding schools are not only educational institutions but also provide tourist and culinary attractions. This certainly cannot be separated from the role of the kiyai in managing it. This view attracts researchers to reveal and study the role of kiyai in making this happen. In substance, this research focuses on analyzing the role of kiyai as managers, motivators, administrators and evaluators in tourism and culinary development. The research method uses a qualitative approach using data mining techniques through observation, documentation and interviews. The research results explain that kiyai have a strategic role in pioneering the development of Sharia-based natural tourism. The efforts made by the kiyai include training, workshops, comparative studies, increasing comfort and security, cultivating sharia tourism and halal culinary, cadre management, empowering students. In leadership, he carries out his role as a manager by planning, coordinating, implementing and evaluating work programs with his subordinates. The role of the kiyai evaluator is active in evaluating activities to determine the successes and obstacles of the planned program. The role of the kiyai as a motivator is very strategic because in Islamic boarding school culture the fatwa or instructions of the kiyai as motivation must be carried out. The role of the kiyai is as an administrator by being the pioneer of orderly administration. All forms of administration must be based on the direction, guidance and knowledge of the kiyai.

Keywords: *Role, Kiyai, Development, Tourism and Culinary*

The Role Of Retail Brand Image In Retail Msme Consumer Loyalty

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Abstract

This research aims to examine the role of retail brand image on retail consumer loyalty by using Retail MSME Attitudes as a mediator. The research design is confirmatory research and explanatory research. The research population is retail MSME consumers who sell basic necessities in Jember Regency. The research sample was taken using a non-probability sampling technique with a purposive sampling method. The total sample was 306 respondents. The data analysis methods used in this research are descriptive statistical analysis and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)-AMOS. The research results show that Store Image does not have a significant effect on consumer loyalty and Store Image has a significant effect on Consumer Loyalty through Retail MSME Attitudes.

Keywords: Retail Brand Image, Attitude of Retail MSMEs, Consumer Loyalty

The Impact Of The Pro-Israel Product Boycott On Stock Prices Companies Registered On Bei

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Abstract

This research aims to analyze the impact of the pro-Israel product boycott on the share prices of companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (BEI). Boycotting pro-Israel products has become a widespread effort carried out by community groups who argue that Israel has violated human rights in Palestine. The method used in this research is a descriptive quantitative method with data analysis techniques using paired T-Test techniques using share price data of companies listed on the IDX during a certain period before and after the boycott of pro-Israel products. The share price data was obtained from trusted sources such as the official IDX website. The results of this research show that there is an impact on the share prices of 6 sample companies from the IDX whose products are pro-Israel.

Keywords: Product Boycott, Stock Prices

Perceptions of Financial Rewards, Professional Training, Work Environment, Job Market Considerations on Selecting a Public Accountant Career.

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Abstract

This research aims to find out how accounting students at Muhammadiyah University of Makassar perceive their choice of a career as a public accountant and whether financial rewards, professional training, work environment are labor market considerations in choosing a career as a public accountant. The research was carried out using the Multiple Linear Regression analysis tool in SPSS. The hypothesis uses the t test with the research results showing that Financial Awards have a significant influence on the choice of a public accountant career, Professional Training and Work Environment have no effect and are not significant on the choice of a public accountant career, Job market considerations have no effect but are significant on the choice of a public accountant career.

Keywords: Financial Rewards, Professional Training, Work Environment, Job Market Considerations, and Public Accounting Careers

Complementary Therapy and Holistic Nursing Care Plan

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Abstract

Complementary therapy regulated fundamental caring principles and integrated as part of nursing care management. Nursing concept model of caring for patients widely opens a chance to encourage individual abilities as a nurse in modifying holistic nursing care plans and also improving nurse-patient relationships. The aim of this study was to determine nursing student's knowledge and the use of complementary therapy in holistic nursing care plans. A descriptive cross sectional survey was performed among nursing students in the Faculty of Health Science who had established nursing care plan and was in final year of education. Participants taken by total sampling (n=115). Questionnaire completed with participants to determine their knowledge, personal methods use and reasons toward complementary therapy. The participants had a good knowledge towards complementary therapy. More than a half of the participants reported that they use of relaxation therapy, herbs, cupping therapy and Qur'an recitation into their nursing care plan so that patients can be treated as a holistic from the side of patients biology, psychology, sociology and spiritualism needs. Nursing students engaged complementary therapy in their nursing care plan. Good knowledge about complementary therapies in nursing students will increase the use of these therapies in providing nursing care. Nurses with the caring concept model are in a strategic position to be able to provide holistic nursing care, one of which is by implementing complementary therapies in the nursing plan.

Keywords: Complementary Therapy; Holistic; Nursing Care Plan

Assessment Of Risk As A Sustainable Coffee Supply Chain Strategy On Rural Area In Jember Regency

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Abstract

Risk assessment is essential for effectively and efficiently evaluating and controlling risks in order to create a sustainable coffee supply chain. The goal of this research is to identify the factors that influence quality risk and risk mitigation in small-holder coffee. The ANP method is used to identify the cause of a problem in the smallholder coffee supply chain by taking into account the occurrence criteria (O), severity (S), and detection (D). Data is gathered through interviews with expert respondents and experts from farmers, cooperatives, agro-industries, researchers, and academics who have been involved in the coffee agro-industry for at least ten years. The analyses' findings reveal a structural model for identifying and prioritizing risks by identifying six factors and 16 sub-factors. According to the findings of this study, farmers' knowledge and skills in terms of cultivation techniques are the main risks of relative importance in the coffee supply chain and thus require attention. Mitigation efforts that can be taken include improvements to cultivation that focus on the management of pests and diseases of coffee plants, as well as technical education and training. Factors that prevent farmers from accessing and implementing training must be considered so that knowledge and skills can be effectively provided.

Keywords: keywords 1; coffee, supply chain, risk assessment, strategy

Quality of Household Compost Products Using The Takakura Method

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Abstract

Takakura Method is one of the simple method to reducing organic waste. This method is making compost from household waste. The purpose of this study is to determine the quality of compost and to determine the effectiveness of the application Takakura Method without special treatment. This research was conducted in the workshop area of the Environmental Engineering Department, Universitas Muhammadiyah Jember. The parameters analyzed include moisture content, temperature, pH, N-total, P₂O₅, K₂O, C-Organik, and C/N Ratio. This research uses descriptive qualitative with an evaluation approach that aims to determine the quality of compost product and compare with SNI Compost and Minister of Agriculture Regulation No. 28 of 2009. The result of examining the quality of the compost, it can be conclude that ini general the quality of compost that produced from Takakura Method (without any special treatment) is good in terms of the level of maturity and suitability with the technical requirements of organic fertilizers.

Keywords: Compost, Takakura Method, SNI Compost, Household Waste

Swot Analysis As A Basis For An Effective Strategy For CCTV Installation Services Business (Case Study At CV. Cbs)

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the company's internal factors, internal and external factors faced by the company and the application of SWOT analysis which can formulate an effective strategy for the CV company. CBS CCTV Banyuwangi. The population studied in this research were Managers, Employees and Consumers of CV. CBS Banyuwangi, which understands directly and indirectly the company's internal and external factors. Data collection methods use observation, interviews and documentation studies. The analysis methods used are the SAP analysis method, ETOP analysis method, and SWOT analysis method. Based on the results of the analysis, there are several strategies that need to be carried out, namely: the company must carry out a joint venture with several similar companies with the aim of pooling resources to carry out certain economic activities or projects simultaneously, the company must make cost savings and narrow down the business and this aims to strengthen its superiority. which distinguishes the distinctive competences owned by the company.

Keywords: SWOT analysis

Confirmed Expectations, And Benefits Perceived By Consumers, On Online Repurchase Intentions With Satisfaction As Mediation

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Abstract

The development of digitalization is increasingly widespread, this is triggered by a pandemic that forces people to use online in all their activities, including marketing products, both goods and services. After the pandemic passed, activities continued normally, of course, followed by a decline in online consumers. Moreover, there are indications of a decline with the large number of online companies (startups) that are laying off workers. How to know consumer intentions to continue purchasing, researchers are interested in conducting research using the expectation confirmation theory. The quantitative analysis method for PLS SEM data uses the Wrap PLS 7.0 tool. Sampling 120 people with the probability sampling method. The result is that expectation confirmation theory has an influence on the formation of sustainable intentions in online purchases in the post-pandemic period with the dominant variable being perceived benefits to form satisfaction to form repurchase intentions in the post-pandemic era.

Keywords: confirmed, perceived, online, satisfaction, intention

Government Policy For The Management and Comparative Study Of Stunting In The Philippines And Indonesia

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Abstract

Two nations with a high rate of stunting prevalence roughly 36% are Indonesia and the Philippines. The governments of the Philippines and Indonesia have attempted to address the phenomenon of stunting in a number of ways, including through various policies, regulations, and interventions. This article attempts to explain the laws and policies pertaining to the prevention of stunting in the Philippines and Indonesia. Many stunting prevention rules and regulations already exist in Indonesia and the Philippines, and they take the shape of sensitive and targeted interventions. The health sector implemented targeted interventions by concentrating on the First 1000 Days of Life (HPK) program; sensitive measures involve granting access to sanitary facilities and clean water. Stunting has been linked to socioeconomic factors, such as family income, education level, and poverty, in addition to health issues. Cross-sector cooperation must occur for stunting prevention, which was done extensively. Centrally established rules and regulations must also be monitored at the regional and local levels, involving not only the health sector but also other relevant sectors. The community's strong knowledge of the value of nutritious food, cleanliness, and sanitation calls for more improvements to the community-based response system. One important tool for lowering stunting rates was the environment.

Keywords: stunting, policies

Effect of Motivation and Compensation on Performance of Jember Regency Paddy Farmer through Job Satisfaction as Intervening Variable

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Abstract

Farmer strengthening is needed to make farmer stand on their profession for supporting food security program. Aimed of this study was, want to know the effect of motivation and compensation on performance of Jember Regency paddy farmer through job satisfaction as intervening variable. Study was done at Jember Regency as the fourth big rice producer in East Java in January 2022 as rainy cultivation season. Sample was 80 farmers consist of 20 farmers form each four Sub District represent four region in Jember. They were Kalisat (north), Ledokombo (east), Ajung (south) and Tanggul (west) chosen because has widest rice filed. Motivation and job satisfaction was measured by Likert scale, beside compensation was mesured by income from paddy farming and performance was measured by land productivity. Data was analized by path analysis. The result were: (1) motivation, compensation and job satisfaction affected 57.30% performance of farmer simultaneously and significant at 1% level meanwhile 42.70% the rest was caused by another factors; (2). motivation and compensatian simultanuosly affected only 9.6% on job satisfaction but significant at 1% test level meanwhile 90.40 % the rest was caused by another factors; (3) motivation affected 1.06 % directly and 0.16% indirectly through job statisfaction on performance of paddy farmer at Jember Regency; (4) compensation affected 53.44% directly and 0.01% indirectly through job statisfaction on performance of paddy farmerat Jember Regency.

Keywords: compensation; motivation; job satisfaction; performance

The Impact of Work Motivation, Work Discipline, Work Culture and Work Environment on Employee Performance at Ambulu Village Office

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Abstract

The reason for this study is to decide the effect of work inspiration, work discipline, work culture, and workplace on representative execution at the Ambulu Town Office. This kind of exploration involves quantitative strategies and the quantity of tests in this review is 30 respondents, the examining strategy utilized is immersed testing or enumeration. Validity tests, reliability tests, classical assumption tests, multiple linear regression analysis, T tests, and R2 tests are the analytical tools utilized in this study. Work motivation, discipline, culture, and the work environment all have a positive and significant impact on employee performance at the Ambulu Village Office, according to this study's findings, which are significant at a level of 0.05%. This should be visible in light of the consequences of the coefficient of assurance (R^2) test that the four autonomous factors influence representative execution at the Ambulu Town Office by 84.1% and the leftover 15.9% are affected by different factors.

Keywords: Work Inspiration; work discipline; Performance, Workplace Culture, and Environment

The Influence of Organizational Culture, Commitment, Compensation, and Work Ethic on Employee Performance at Djoglo Larisso Jember

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Abstract

This research aims to comprehensively analyze the impact of organizational culture, commitment, compensation, and work ethic on employee performance at Djoglo Larisso Jember. Employing a quantitative approach and correlational research design, the entire employee population (n=32) at Djoglo Larisso participated. The findings reveal that each independent variable, namely organizational culture, commitment, compensation, and work ethic, significantly influences employee performance both partially and simultaneously. The collective influence of these factors on employee performance at Djoglo Larisso underscores their interdependence. This study concludes that, when addressed collectively, these elements significantly contribute to the enhancement of employee performance. The practical implication emphasizes the imperative for culinary business owners to holistically incorporate and manage these factors to fortify the competitiveness and sustainability of their ventures in the highly competitive culinary industry. Further research may delve into more detailed strategies for the effective implementation of these variables in the culinary context, fostering a deeper understanding of their nuanced impact.

Keywords: Commitment; Compensation; Employee Performance; Organizational Culture; Work Ethic.

Influence Of Store Atmosphere, Prices, And Service Quality On Consumer Satisfaction At The Blink-Blink Store

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to find out and analyze whether store atmosphere, price and service quality have a significant effect on consumer satisfaction at the Blink-Blink Store. The population used in this research was all consumers at the Blink-Blink Store, and the number of samples used was 40 respondents. The data analysis method used is multiple linear regression analysis. The results of this research are: 1) Store Atmosphere (X1) has no significant effect on Consumer Satisfaction (Y) at Blink-Blink Store in Jember. 2) Price (X2) has no significant effect on the Consumer Satisfaction variable (Y1) at Blink-Blink Store in Jember. 3) Service Quality (X3) has a significant effect on the Consumer Satisfaction variable (Y1) at the Blink-Blink Store in Jember.

Keywords: store atmosphere, price and service quality, Blink-Blink Store

Study Of The Influence Of *Brand Image, Lifestyle, Store Atmosphere* And Service Quality On Purchasing Decisions At Starbucks In Jember City

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the effect of brand image, lifestyle, store atmosphere and service quality on purchase decision in Starbucks Jember. The population in this study is all consumers who have made purchase at Starbucks Jember. The samples used were 60 respondents who were consumers who had dine-in purchases at Starbucks Jember. The sampling technique used is purposive sampling. The method of data analysis uses multiple linear regression with help of SPSS 20. The test used is data instrument test (validity and reliability), the classic assumption test (normality test, multicollinearity test, and heteroscedasticity test), analysis multiple linear regression, coefficient of determination (R^2), hypothesis test (t test and F test). The results showed that partially brand image has a significant effect on purchase decision; lifestyle has a significant effect on purchase decision; store atmosphere has significant effect on purchase decision; service quality has no significant effect on purchase decision; brand image, lifestyle, store atmosphere, service quality has significant effect on purchase decision in Starbucks Jember.

Keywords :brand image, lifestyle, store atmosphere, service quality ,and purchase *Decision*

Collaborative Governance In Empowering Msmes To Extreme Poverty Reduction In Baubau City

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Abstract

The extreme poverty reduction program is the main development agenda of the Baubau City regional government to reduce it from 0.93 percent to 0 percent by 2024. On the other hand, the extreme poverty reduction program requires multi-stakeholder collaboration, as well as effective empowerment based on the development needs of the MSME group. The aim of this research is to analyze the concept of collaborative governance in empowering MSME groups in Baubau City, in order to reduce extreme poverty rates. This research was carried out qualitatively, by measuring data on the distribution of extreme poverty in Baubau City, the Depth Index, and the Poverty Severity Index with a map of the distribution of the number of MSMEs in Baubau City. In general, the results of this research show that statistically MSMEs continue to grow with the diversity of their business units, and have an influence on the absorption capacity of the workforce. However, the characteristics of existing MSMEs are very diverse, so they require appropriate empowerment program implications to have a positive influence on alleviating extreme poverty in Baubau City. Therefore, this research indicates that it provides input for stakeholders involved in empowering MSMEs as well as academic implications for policy makers in reducing the rate of extreme poverty in Baubau City.

Smart Strategy Synergy Of Government Administration In The Sub-District (Study in Rogojampi District, Banyuwangi Regency)

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Abstract

Background: Practicality requires bureaucrats to be more innovative and effective in leading and administering government affairs. Young & transparent access to information, digitization, and services to the public that are very serving, are important components that must be owned by government agencies at various levels. The East Java Provincial Government Administration Synergy Competition (SP2K) in 2022 is a way to test the sophistication of governance synergy at the sub-district level. Uniquely, Rogojampi District won first place in the SP2K competition. **Purpose:** This study aims to determine the strategy used by the District of Rogojampi, as a sub-district with good governance at the sub-district level. The results of the research can serve as an example for sub-districts in Indonesia, which will then be adopted for their success in order to lead to the synergy of good governance. **Research Methods:** Using qualitative research methods, the data collection is through interviews with Rogojampi District officials, literature studies from various sources & documentation of government administration activities. **Research Results:** Research shows that Rogojampi District has carried out the mandate in Government Regulation Number 17 of 2018 concerning Districts on the subject of innovation and public service well. The Rogojampi sub-district head, as the main figure in carrying out general government tasks at the sub-district level, has carried out synergies and collaborations, so that his government practices give birth to innovations that are beneficial to the community, Rogojampi District Creative Innovation; Hacker Production House, Posting Dong, Yamin Perkasa, Pak Asmat, and GROBAKS.

Policy Innovations for Digitalizing Sustainability: Reshaping The Governance Landscape for MSMEs in Jember

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Abstract

In the context of global transformation that sparked by digitalization, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Jember Regency face significant challenges. This research aims to reveal the dynamics experienced by MSMEs, identify policy issues, and design an innovative policy framework that supports the sustainability of MSMEs in the digital era. The purpose of this research is to provide an in-depth understanding of the role of policy in shaping a sustainable MSME ecosystem in the digital era. This research uses a qualitative method by conducting a literature review. The results reveal the dynamics and future opportunities related to the sustainability and digitalization of MSMEs at the local level. The resulting policy recommendations have strategic implications for policy makers and practitioners, with the aim of making a significant contribution to the sustainability of MSMEs in Jember Regency amid the changing dynamics of the global economy. This research anticipates offering practical guidance to navigate future challenges and outlines strategic steps for ensuring the sustainable growth of MSMEs in the digital era.

facilitative leadership from the perspective of collaborative governance in village development

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Abstract

This study aims to explain how facilitative leadership factors in village development using the concept of collaborative governance by looking at the development experience of Sidomulyo Village. Village development begins with the digital village program which has the risk of transparency of village programs and finances, secondly the village head dares to follow the regional government's policy for tourism villages, and thirdly the foreign exchange village program. The village development program was able to bring the village status to an independent village from the previous status of a developing village. This analysis explores how the leadership of the village head uses the concept of collaborative governance in each development program, the leadership framework in the perspective of Collaborative Governance According to Angsel and Gass, facilitative leadership is one of the factors to support the Collaborative Governance process. The research method used in the research is a qualitative method by developing the implementation of FGDs to find out each actor to be able to assess the role of leadership in the Sidomulyo Village Collaborative Governance Process. Research findings, show that 2 important factors of leadership roles make an important contribution to collaborative governance, first, Social Capital with aspects of the ability to create networks into the community and outward networks, the ability to carry out conflict resolution, the ability to understand local potential. Second, institutional capability with aspects of the ability to plan activities and finances, the ability to implement with the involvement of community groups and private / other interested parties, the ability to monitor village development activities with openness and public involvement.

Business Model Innovation To Increase Msme Competitiveness: A Strategic Design Approach

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Abstract

One key to the success of MSME in facing global competition is their ability to innovate their business models. Innovative business models can enhance operational efficiency, expand market share, and respond quickly to changing consumer needs. In this context, the Strategic Design approach serves as a relevant and significant foundation. This research aims to analyze the main challenges faced by MSME, identify innovative practices in SME business models, measure the impact of business model innovation on SME competitiveness, and develop a strategic design framework to support the growth and sustainability of MSME. The research employs SWOT analysis as the first step, analyzing data obtained by examining internal and external factors of the companies. The subsequent step involves matching internal and external factors to create strategies. In addition to SWOT analysis, data is obtained and analyzed through interviews and focus group discussions with MSME owners and customers, using these techniques to gain in-depth insights into the business and provide a platform for exchanging ideas to discover innovative business model ideas that can develop MSME. The conclusion of this research is as follows: firstly, it is crucial for MSME to overcome limited access to capital and enhance managerial skills. Government initiatives and industry partnerships can assist in providing the necessary resources and training. Secondly, MSME need to promote the adoption of digital technology and collaborate with others to create added value. Creative marketing strategies and product diversification can also help MSME differentiate themselves from competitors. Thirdly, improving SME competitiveness through business model innovation can have positive economic and social impacts. Stakeholders need to support innovation by creating a supportive environment and removing barriers. Lastly, the framework obtained can serve as a guide for MSME to develop sustainable business strategies. Stakeholders, including the government and institutions supporting MSME, need to collaborate in implementing this framework.

The Impact of Board Size and Audit Committee Characteristics on Financial Performance in Foreign Exchange Banks: Evidence from Indonesia

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Abstract

The concept of corporate governance (CG) has become a topic of interest in accounting and finance. This plays an important role, especially in the process of submitting financial reports. However, the literature reveals inconsistent findings regarding the impact of corporate governance characteristics on financial performance. Despite numerous studies on corporate governance, there remains a lack of evidence, particularly in the banking industry, specifically concerning foreign exchange banks in Indonesia. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the influence of board size and audit committee characteristics, namely audit committee size, frequency of audit committee meetings, and audit committee expertise, as integral components of corporate governance, on financial performance. Secondary data obtained from the annual reports published by the Financial Services Authority (OJK) and the websites of 38 foreign exchange banks in Indonesia from 2007 to 2021 were utilized for the study. The research findings indicate that board size exhibits a non-significant negative relationship with financial performance measured by Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE). In addition, the results regarding audit committee size and frequency of meetings show no significant relationship with ROA and ROE proxies financial performance. However, audit committee expertise shows a significant negative relationship with financial performance as measured by ROE, and not significant with ROA. In conclusion, this research highlights the importance of corporate governance mechanisms which can prove useful for policy makers in designing future strategies. In addition, these findings will assist management in making informed decisions regarding optimizing board size and audit committee characteristics to meet the needs and interests of all stakeholders within the company. Overall, this

research emphasizes the need for continuous improvement in corporate governance practices for sustainable growth and development

Legal Protection of Women's Rights as Heads of Families in Running a Typical Buton Weaving Business

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Abstract

The existence of women in the family environment has a very urgent role. This role is not only in the private aspect but also the domestic aspect. The aim of this research is to analyze the fulfillment of women's rights as heads of families in running the Typical Buton Weaving Business . This type of research uses empirical legal research. The data source is primary data obtained directly in Wabula Village. Data collection techniques use observation, interviews and literature study. Data analysis uses qualitative data, namely the results of data in the field are analyzed to obtain answers to the research objectives. The results of the research show that legally the rights of women wabula weavers have been granted by the government. One of the rights obtained is the right to get a decent job and the right to get a decent salary. The Buton Regency Regional Government has facilitated woven materials that will be used by weavers. The suggestion from this research is that the local government needs to form a weaving group and create a regeneration of young weavers (young people) to continue the weaving heritage in Buton Regency

Analysis of the Human Development Index and Economic Empowerment of MSMEs towards Harmony and Community Sectoral Ego Culture in Situbondo

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Abstract

This research analyze the correlation between human development index and economic empowerment on community harmony and welfare in Situbondo. Strategies for strengthening religious harmony and national early vigilance in a sectoral ego culture, especially policies regarding fostering religious harmony and handling conflict, can be more focused and targeted, especially in the context of providing early warnings to anticipate various potential forms of conflict, ATHG (Threats, Challenges, Obstacles, and Disturbances), The research was conducted in moderate villages, namely Wonorejo Village and Sumberkolak Village, Situbondo. The research results show that there is a relationship between the human development index and efforts to increase economic empowerment through strengthening MSMEs. The development index is in line with the economic activity of MSMEs so that it can reduce economic disparities which are one of the triggers for religious harmony conflict problems. Increasing community economic income can reduce inequality, increase harmony, quality of life and welfare of the community in Situbondo. In each decade phase, the Indonesian government at the national, regional and regional levels must be able to anticipate the emergence of socio-cultural dynamics that give rise to sectoral ego culture. Will these socio-cultural dynamics be responded to as positive and supportive social capital, or will they become social capital that hinders development, the economy, harmony and improving the quality of human life.

Keywords: harmony; human development; MSMEs; ego culture sectoral

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Abstract

Practicality requires bureaucrats to be more innovative and effective in leading and administering government affairs. Young & transparent access to information, digitization, and services to the public that are very serving, are important components that must be owned by government agencies at various levels. The East Java Provincial Government Administration Synergy Competition (SP2K) in 2022 is a way to test the sophistication of governance synergy at the sub-district level. Uniquely, Rogojampi District won first place in the SP2K competition. This study aims to determine the strategy used by the District of Rogojampi, as a sub-district with good governance at the sub-district level. The results of the research can serve as an example for sub-districts in Indonesia, which will then be adopted for their success in order to lead to the synergy of good governance. Using qualitative research methods, the data collection is through interviews with Rogojampi District officials, literature studies from various sources & documentation of government administration activities. Research shows that Rogojampi District has carried out the mandate in Government Regulation Number 17 of 2018 concerning Districts on the subject of innovation and public service well. The Rogojampi sub-district head, as the main figure in carrying out general government tasks at the sub-district level, has carried out synergies and collaborations, so that his government practices give birth to innovations that are beneficial to the community, Rogojampi District Creative Innovation; Hacker Production House, Posting Dong, Yamin Perkasa, Pak Asmat, and GROBAKS.

Keywords: Innovation, Governance, Subdistrict, SP2K

Lecturers' Readiness Level Analysis of Home-Based Learning Readiness Based on ICT Efficacy and Attitude

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Abstract

The pandemic period is not over, but teaching and learning activities are still ongoing. However, teaching activities process must still be carried out even though sometimes the room and distance between lectures and students must change the teaching and learning activities process carried out entirely at home that is commonly referred to as home-based learning (HBL). Meanwhile, the implementation requires readiness from both lecturers and students. In this study, lecturer readiness can be seen from two factors, namely ICT efficacy and attitude toward home-based learning. The research purpose is the institution and leaders can consider the right steps to increase the readiness of lecturers in teaching later. This research approach uses qualitative descriptive. The collecting data techniques use observation, interviews, and questionnaires. The results of this study for the ICT efficacy factor have met the readiness level with average value of 4.22, that means they are ready to move forward, while the attitude factor also have met the readiness level with average value of 4.04, that means they are ready but need a few improvements.

Keywords: lecturer's readiness; home-based learning readiness; ICT efficacy; attitude
